

STUDIES IN COMPLEX FORMATION WITH COLLOIDAL MERCURI-SULPHOSALICYLIC ACID. PART I. COMPLEX BERYLLIUM MERCURI-SULPHOSALICYLATE

By RAJENDRA S. SINGH AND SATYA PRAKASH

Mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid forms complexes with metal ions similar to those obtained with sulphosalicylic acid, as it possesses the same co-ordinating groups. Potentiometric and conductometric studies reveal that mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid forms two types of complexes with beryllium: (i) 1:1 complex in acidic medium and (ii) 1:2 complex in alkaline medium. Both the complexes are very stable as the beryllium is not precipitated from the complex even in highly alkaline solutions. In both the complexes, the phenolic hydrogen is displaced during complex formation.

The mercury compounds of sulphophenol carboxylic acid and their homologues (Saccharin, Fabrik Aktien-Gesellschaft vorm. Fahlberg List and Co., *British Chem. Abs.*, 1920, 673), when dispersed in water, yield colloidal solutions. Ostwald (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1926, 23, 242) investigated the colloidal nature of complex mercury derivatives of sulphosalicylic acid. As mercury forms a compound of structure $C_6H_4-COOH-HgOH$ with benzoic acid and a compound of structure $C_6H_3-OH-COOH-HgOH$ with salicylic acid, Ostwald has assigned the structure of mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid as $HO_2S-C_6H_3-OH-COOH-HgOH$. Since this compound possesses the same co-ordinating groups as sulphosalicylic acid, it forms complexes similar to those obtained with the latter.

EXPERIMENTAL

Colloidal Mercuri-sulphosalicylic Acid.—From a solution of mercuric chloride (A.R., B.D.H.) mercuric oxide was precipitated by the addition of an excess of NaOH solution, and the precipitate thoroughly washed with distilled water till free of hydroxyl and chloride ions. The precipitate was dissolved in a concentrated solution of sulphosalicylic acid (G.R., E. Merck), the ratio of the oxide to acid being 1:2. The white gel, obtained on drying over a water-bath, furnished a greyish solid, which was washed with alcohol to free it of excess of unchanged sulphosalicylic acid. The powder obtained on drying was white and hygroscopic. This, when dissolved in water, gave a clear transparent colloidal solution. Solutions of requisite strength were prepared by dissolving a known amount of the powder and finally standardised by titration against a standard alkali solution. Due to the high viscosity of the colloidal solution, solutions of concentrations above 0.07M could not be prepared at room temperatures (below 30°). The mercury of the colloid was estimated gravimetrically as HgS. The ratio of mercury to sulphosalicylic acid in the compound was found 1:1, thus confirming Ostwald's formula of colloidal mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid.

In the study of the complex formation with mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid and beryllium ions, it was not possible to use the colloidal solution, as coagulation occurred due to the free electrolyte present. Hence, potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate, obtained by the addition of an excess of potassium chloride to the colloid, was used in place of mercuri-sulphosalicylate. A solution of this compound in water behaves like a true solution. The monosodium salt of this compound was obtained by neutralisation with a calculated volume of a standard alkali solution.

Standard solutions of beryllium sulphate were prepared by direct weighing of A.R., B.D.H. $\text{BeSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and dissolution in water. Fresh solutions have been employed, as stocked solutions are known to undergo hydrolysis.

All measurements were done at a constant temperature of $32^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The electrical conductivity was measured with Leeds Northrup's Kohlrausch Slidewire, with an audiofrequency oscillator in the circuit. The conductivity cell was one with cell constant of 0.1400, and the point of balance detected by a headphone.

The p_H measurements were made with Leeds Northrup's A.C.-operated p_H -meter, using glass and saturated calomel electrodes. The instrument was calibrated with a standard buffer solution, and gave readings accurate to 0.02 units over the p_H scale.

Complex-forming Systems

In the study of complex formation of beryllium (II) with potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate and its monosodium salt, the monovariant method was used. To a constant volume of beryllium sulphate solution were added varying amounts of complexing agent, keeping the total volume constant. Thus, a number of mixtures containing beryllium sulphate and the complexing agent in the ratios of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:4 were prepared. These mixtures were then titrated against a standard caustic soda solution. A known volume of the mixture was taken and to it varying quantities of alkali solutions were added, keeping the volume constant. The mixtures were left in a thermostat to attain equilibrium, after which the specific conductivity and p_H measurements were made. For comparison, the specific conductivity and p_H studies were made also separately with beryllium sulphate and potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate solutions, when titrated with alkali under similar conditions.

The typical reproducible results obtained out of a large number of experiments performed are shown in Figs. 1-5.

D I S C U S S I O N

Before investigating the complex formation between beryllium and mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid, it was thought to be of interest to make some observations on the nature of colloidal mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid. The effects of potassium chloride, potassium bromide, potassium thiocyanate, potassium nitrate and potassium sulphate on the colloidal nature of mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid have been studied. The results are graphically represented in Fig. 1, where curves a,b,c,d and e represent the changes

It has been shown by Ostwald (*loc. cit.*) and Thiele (*Kolloid Z.*, 1952, 127, 134) that the effect of Cl^- , Br^- and CNS^- on mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid is a case of true chemical combination, as equivalent amounts of the reactants are required. The reaction has been represented as (I).

Fig. 2 represents the changes in the p_H that take place when beryllium sulphate, potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate and their mixtures in different proportions are titrated with alkali respectively. The abscissa represents the number of equivalents (a) of alkali added per gram ion of hydrogen of the mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid.

FIG. 2

Curves A to D are for solutions that are $6.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ in beryllium sulphate with no added potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate and with 1, 2 and 4 equivalents added respectively. Curves E and F are for $6.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ solutions of mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid and potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate.

From the graph it can be seen that the addition of hydroxyl ions to beryllium sulphate does not cause immediate precipitation. Over one equivalent of alkali has to be added before precipitation starts, and is complete when two equivalents have been added. This has also been reported by Britton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2121). The reaction may be represented as:

The neutralisation of mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid (Fig. 2, curve F) shows one sharp inflexion at $\alpha = 2$, which indicates that the colloid behaves like a dibasic acid.

The phenolic hydrogen does not ionise even at high values of p_{H} .

Potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate (curve E) shows two definite inflexions, one at $\alpha = 1$ and the other at $\alpha = 2$. The first inflexion occurs at p_{H} range 3.50–6.50, indicating the ionisation of the carboxyl hydrogen only.

The second inflexion at the p_{H} range 8.0–11.0 indicates the ionisation of the phenolic hydrogen also.

With one equivalent of potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate added to beryllium sulphate (curve B) no decrease in the initial p_{H} of the mixture is observed, but there is an inflexion at $\alpha = 2$. The beryllium of the complex formed is not precipitated even at high values of p_{H} (10.0), which shows the stability of the complex. The reaction may be represented by equation as:

This suggests that the phenolic hydrogen is displaced during complex formation.

With 2 and 4 equivalents of potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate added to beryllium sulphate (Fig. 2, curves C and D), the behaviour is different. Curve C shows an inflexion at $\alpha = 4$ and curve D, at $\alpha = 6$, respectively. This indicates that a mol. of beryllium co-ordinates with two potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate mols. to form an 1:2 complex. This complex also is very stable, as the beryllium is not precipitated. The reaction may be represented as:

The excess of potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate remains ionised in solution.

Fig. 3 represents the changes in p_{H} when solutions, that are $3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$ in (i) beryllium sulphate (curve A), (ii) 1:1 and 1:4 mixtures of beryllium with monosodium potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate (curves B & C) are titrated with alkali respectively. The abscissa represents the number of equivalents of alkali added (a) The addition of alkali to beryllium sulphate has already been discussed (vide equation 1). The 1:1 mixture of beryllium ion and monosodium potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate (curve B) has an initial p_{H} (3.10) which is lower than both that of beryllium sulphate (3.95) or the monosodium salt (6.10) alone, showing an

increase in the hydrogen-ion concentration of the mixture. There is an inflexion in the p_H curve at $a=1$, and the beryllium of the complex formed is not precipitated even in alkaline solution. This indicates clearly that the phenolic hydrogen is displaced during complex formation, according to the equation :

FIG. 3

Equivs. of alkali added (a).

FIG. 4

Equivs. of alkali added (a).

With 1:4 mixture (curve C) the behaviour is different. The initial p_H of the mixture is lower than that of the beryllium sulphate and monosodium salt alone, but the inflexion occurs at $a=2$. This indicates that the complex formed contains beryllium ion and the monosodium salt in the ratio of 1:2. The beryllium of the complex is not precipitated even in alkaline solutions. The reaction may be represented as :

Fig. 4 represents the changes in the specific conductivity when solutions, that are $3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$ in (i) beryllium sulphate (curve A), (ii) 1:1 mixtures of beryllium with potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate (curve B) and its monosodium salt (curve C) respectively, (iii) potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate (curve D), and

(iv) mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid (curve E), are titrated with alkali respectively. The abscissa represents the number of equivalents of alkali added (a). The neutralisation of potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate (curve D) shows a minima at $a=1$ and discontinuity in the graph at $a=2$, according to equations (3) and (4). The neutralisation of mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid (curve E) also shows a minima at $a=1$ and a discontinuity at $a=2$, whereas the p_H curve (Fig. 2, curve E) shows only one inflexion at $a=2$, according to equation (2). It seems probable that the minima is due to the replacement of sulphonic hydrogen by sodium, as it is more acidic than the carboxyl hydrogen.

The addition of alkali to beryllium sulphate (curve A) produces little change in the conductivity values in the beginning, but it increases sharply after the addition of two equivalents of alkali ($a=2$); the reaction may therefore be represented by equation (1).

The addition of alkali to 1:1 mixtures of beryllium ions with potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate and its monosodium salt (Fig. 4, curves B and C) shows minima at $a=2$ and $a=1$, respectively. The solutions behave as if it were of a dibasic and monobasic acids (vide equations 5 and 7). This gives clear evidence that a complex is being formed and that the phenolic hydrogen is displaced during complexation. The co-ordination takes place between the oxygen atoms of carboxyl and sulphonic groups.

Fig. 5 represents the p_H changes that take place when beryllium sulphate is added to monosodium potassium chloromercuri-sulphosalicylate. Curve A represents the p_H of the mixture solutions while curve A' represents the p_H of beryllium sulphate alone. The p_H of the monosodium salt

decreases with the addition of beryllium and becomes nearly constant when one equivalent has been added. As the mixture curve A lies below the beryllium sulphate curve A', it shows that there is an increase in the hydrogen ion concentration which can only be explained due to the displacement of phenolic hydrogen during complex-formation (vide equation 7).